

D2.4 Report on potential strategic interactions with EU projects and initiatives

WP2 Integrative Strategic Research Agenda

Responsible Partner: VISAVET-UCM

Contributing partners: RIVM, Anses, Sciensano,
BfR, SSI, IP, UoS, ISS, WBVR, INSA, SVA

GENERAL INFORMATION

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Report on potential strategic interactions with EU projects and initiatives

The WP2 «Strategic Research Agenda» has three main objectives: i) Identification and updating priority research and integrative topics in the domains of foodborne zoonoses (FBZ), antimicrobial resistance (AMR) and emerging threats (ET); ii) Developing the Strategic Research Agenda (SRA) providing the basis for the second internal call for Joint Research Projects (WP3) and Joint Integrative Projects (WP4); and iii) Fostering strategic interactions with related EU projects and initiatives.

Objectives

The objective of this procedure (D2.4) is to define and identify the potential strategic interactions with EU projects and initiatives. To fulfil this objective, the information gathered in D2.3. «Report on the identification of relevant EU projects and initiatives and the procedure to identify potential strategic interactions» and MS.23 «Inventory of relevant EU research projects and related initiatives» will be taken into account. The following information will be included in the inventory to facilitate the identification of potential strategic interactions:

- Table with basic information regarding the projects/initiatives (acronym of the project, full name, contact person and e-mail, coordinator's institution and website).
- Information Sheet for each project/initiative, including name of the project/initiative, acronym, logo, website, contact person (e-mail), coordinator's institution, website, funding programme, duration, total budget, consortium, objectives and work programmes.
- Gantt chart or at least actual start and end date to show each project duration.
- OHEJP partners (institution and project contact person) (if any) involved in the identified projects/initiatives.
- OHEJP matrix figure to visualise the scientific scope of the relevant projects/initiatives.

This information will be collected from the CORDIS database, as well as OHEJP partners, and will be updated three times a year. Moreover, it will be available to all OHEJP partners through the password-protected area of the One Health EJP website (intranet/members' area).

Impact

The information about the ongoing projects/initiatives will have an impact in the following OHEJP activities:

a) **Updating priority topics – Strategic Research Agenda (WP2)**. As described in Deliverable D2.2 «Report on the Procedure for Updating Priority Topics», meetings will be organized with the Project Management Team (PMT) and experts to discuss the procedure/criteria for the prioritization of the topics taking into account, among others, the strategic interactions and possible redundancy with other EU projects/initiatives.

b) **Joint Research/Integrative Projects (WP3/WP4)**. The objectives and outputs from certain current or just finished EU projects/initiatives may have an impact on the OHEJP JRPs and JIPs with regard to their deliverables/milestones. Moreover, in the development and evaluation of the second round projects, links to current or recently finished EU projects/initiatives will be an important aspect in order to create synergies and to avoid any redundancy.

c) **Cogwheel Workshops (WP4)**. The choice of strategic initiatives to target for cogwheel workshops (MS.47 «Cogwheel workshop protocol») will be defined and identified taking into account the current projects/initiatives relevant to the OHEJP.

d) **International Stakeholders (WP5)**. As described in Deliverable D5.2 «Report on the Procedure to identify research and integrative needs of international stakeholders», some EU projects' coordinators are part of Stakeholder Committee (SC) and WP5 will interact with WP2 to evaluate whether the identified research and integrative needs and gaps by the Stakeholders are already being addressed in ongoing EU projects/initiatives.

e) **PhD projects (WP6)**. As defined in the «Guidelines for applicants within the OHEJP for PhD Grants», the topic of the PhD projects must be within the scope of the SRA and avoid redundancy with other EU projects/initiatives.

Selection of EU projects/initiatives

The **Strategic Research Agenda (SRA), objectives and expected outcomes** of current relevant EU projects/initiatives will be evaluated in order to prioritise and decide which EU projects/initiatives are more important for OHEJP to align with. The data compiled in MS.23 «Inventory of relevant EU research projects and related initiatives» will provide valuable information regarding the degree of overlap with the OHEJP matrix (themes and domains), Gantt chart, OHEJP partners, overlap with ongoing JRP/JIP, PhD projects, etc. The WP leader/deputy leader, mainly from WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5 WP6, will present their selection and justifications to the **PMT for validation** regarding priority topics (updated SRA), new cogwheel workshops and Stakeholder's interests.

The EU project/initiative's database will be updated every four months from data recorded in the CORDIS database. Other useful information from OHEJP partners should be informed to the WP2 Team.

Strategic Interactions

1. Interaction with the coordinator of relevant EU projects/initiatives.

Once the potential interaction with a specific EU project/initiative has been defined, any member of the PMT (mainly WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5 and WP6 leaders or deputy leaders) could contact the coordinator of the relevant EU project/initiative in order to explore possible collaborations or integrations. In specific cases, cogwheel workshops will be organised by WP4 to further explore possibilities for collaboration (see point 4 below). The OHEJP partners involved in other EU projects/initiatives will be specified in the database to facilitate the first contacts mainly by e-mail or phone.

This interaction could be two ways since coordinators of other EU initiatives/projects could contact the OHEJP partners looking for information and possible future collaborations. In both cases, all the active interactions to identify common strategic objectives and potential synergies should be informed to the OHEJP coordinator and WP2 leader/deputy leader for reporting (MS.24 «List of strategic synergies with EU projects and strategic developments»).

2. Attendance to congresses or workshops of relevant EU projects/initiatives.

Congresses and workshops are an up to date opportunity to know the research activities developed in other EU projects/initiatives. All this information valuable for the OHEJP activities (SRA, cogwheel, development of JRP and JIP, etc.) should be informed to the WP2 Team to update the database and inform the PMT. OHEJP partners could decide to attend congresses/workshops of relevant EU projects/initiatives related with their areas of expertise although, he/she could also attend it after a PMT request to explore future collaborations and to present the OHEJP activities to the Scientific Community.

3. Organization of cogwheel workshops (CW).

OHEJP subtask 4.3.1 «Alignment with strategic initiatives at EU level» is aimed to support integration and alignment with external actors to avoid redundancy mainly for JRP and JIP. Eight cogwheel workshops (CW) will be organized during the lifespan of the OHEJP in order to identify synergies, priorities and opportunities for collaboration. Several criteria (timeline, expected impact, alignment with OHEJP areas of interest, overlap with ongoing JRP/JIP activities, etc.) will be taken into account when selecting the candidate EU projects/initiatives by WP4 leader/deputy leader, in collaboration with WP2, WP3, WP5 and WP6. After the selection, the selected EU projects/initiatives will be presented and justified to the PMT for validation.

4. Interaction with Stakeholders.

As described in Deliverable D5.2 «Report on the Procedure to identify research and integrative needs of international stakeholders» some EU projects' coordinators (COMPARE, EFFORT and JPIAMR) are part of the Stakeholder Committee (SC) and therefore their participation will be crucial to identify research and integrative needs and gaps. The External Scientific Advisory Board (ESAB) will also participate in the identification of gaps and avoid redundancy.

WP5 (Science to Policy) will interact with WP2 to evaluate whether the identified research and integrative needs and gaps by major stakeholders are already being addressed in other research consortia. The updated EU projects/initiatives database will be used for this purpose.